

COMPARING THE OUTCOMES OF LOCAL STEROID INJECTION AND THERAPEUTIC ULTRASOUND IN LATERAL EPICONDYLITIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17301946>

Keywords

Functional disability, Lateral epicondylitis, Local steroid injection tennis elbow, Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation, Therapeutic ultrasound.

Article History

Received: 13 Dec 2024

Accepted: 23 Jan 2025

Published: 04 Feb 2025

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Abstract

Objective: "To compare local steroid injection and therapeutic ultrasound in the treatment of lateral epicondylitis".

Study design: Quasi Experimental Trial.

Study place and duration: Orthopedics Department KRL Hospital Islamabad for 06 months (Feb-Jul 2024)

Patients and methods: 200 patients were divided into two groups. The first group was treated with Local Steroid Injection and the rest with Ultrasound. Each patient received a total of eight sessions of ultrasound therapy during the first 4 weeks of treatment with twice weekly sessions. Efficacy of the treatment modalities was evaluated at 1 and 6 weeks using the Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation questionnaire. Data analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v.25.

Results: The mean age in local steroid injection group was 40.64 ± 11.96 years while in ultrasound group was 38.46 ± 11.20 years. At baseline the mean pain score was 40.33 ± 5.83 vs. 38.79 ± 6.03 (p -value >0.05) that was reduced to 11.35 ± 4.89 vs. 16.75 ± 4.33 after 6 weeks respectively (p -value <0.05). At baseline the mean functional disability score was 44.75 ± 8.97 vs. 44.85 ± 8.43 (p -value >0.05) that was reduced to 15.55 ± 3.70 vs. 19.46 ± 3.80 after 6 weeks respectively (p -value <0.05). At baseline the mean usual activities score was 29.72 ± 6.29 vs. 29.26 ± 5.72 (p -value >0.05) that was reduced to 7.76 ± 3.66 vs. 11.44 ± 2.54 , respectively (p -value <0.05) after 6 weeks.

Conclusion: Thus, local steroid injection is better than therapeutic ultrasound in functionality of elbow joint.

INTRODUCTION

Tennis elbow is another name for lateral epicondylitis, which is caused by overuse of the humerus's lateral epicondyle. This disease is typically associated with irritation of the common extensor origins of the Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis.^{1, 2} Additionally, the anterior edge of the Extensor In 30% of instances, Digitorum Communis is implicated. In rare cases, the bottom of the Extensor Carpi Radialis Longus or the origin of the Extensor

Carpi Ulnaris may sustain injury. Initially, this illness was described as a degenerative process by Dr. Nirschl and Pettrone, not an inflammatory one, but mostly involves the Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis.^{3, 4} Lateral epicondylitis affects less than 5% of tennis players and impacts 1% to 3% of the general population, particularly those involved in activities requiring repetitive wrist actions.⁵

Diagnosis of lateral epicondylitis is confirmed through a thorough physical examination and specific tests, such as the Cozen and Mill tests. Following a diagnosis, the goals of therapy are to manage discomfort, maintain range of motion, retain strength and flexibility, and gradually build endurance. A systematic method for tracking pain and functional impairment is the Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation (PRTEE) questionnaire.^{6, 7} NSAIDs, or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines, are the main therapeutic intervention. To reduce symptoms, local steroid injections are frequently used into the extensor tendon. Therapeutic ultrasound, another treatment method, primarily uses heat to alleviate symptoms, enhancing local metabolism, blood flow, tissue flexibility, and nerve conduction, thereby reducing pain and improving joint mobility.^{8, 9} Several studies conducted in Pakistan have compared ultrasound therapy for lateral epicondylitis with other treatment modalities.¹⁰ However, there are none comparing local steroid injections and therapeutic ultrasound for tennis elbow in Pakistan. Moreover, it is evident from the literature, treatment outcomes vary based on geographic demographics. This study aimed to fill this gap by providing comprehensive data comparing these treatment methods, ultimately determining the most suitable approach for our demographics in Pakistan to tailor treatment modalities for better patient care.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This Quasi Experimental Trial was done at Orthopaedics Department of KRL Hospital Islamabad for about 6 months (Feb 2024-Jul 2024). By using OpenEpi.com, sample size of 200 cases; 100 in each group was calculated with Significance level = 5%, power of study 80% and mean PRTEE Function Disability Score by 12.2 ± 6.4 for corticosteroid injection group vs 14.6 ± 5.5 for ultrasound therapy group.⁴ All the patients who fulfilled following selection criteria were enrolled by applying Non-probability Consecutive Sampling technique.

Inclusion of patients: Patients of age 20-60 year of either gender, having lateral elbow pain as diagnosed by Southampton's Diagnostic Criteria, which is as follows: (i) pain in lateral epicondyle in resistant active extension of wrist; (ii) pain in lateral epicondyle for 24 hours or more in last week; (iii) sensitivity on lateral epicondyle.

Exclusion of patients:

Patients with recent trauma or surgery of same site, rheumatoid arthritis, structural abnormality, cervical radiculopathy, contraindications of steroid use and carpal tunnel syndrome

The study was conducted after the approval from the Institutional Review Board (KRL-HI-PUB-ERC/24/03 dated 24 Jan 2024) of KRL Hospital, Islamabad. The baseline data including the patient's age, gender, BMI, smoking habits, and previous treatment history was collected from all the patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria. Informed consent was taken regarding both the treatment modalities for inclusion into the study. The patients were divided into two treatment groups after deciding for treatment by patient. The member of the first group were treated with Local Steroid Injection and the rest with Therapeutic Ultrasound. The subjects were advised not to do any strenuous activity with the affected arm that could exacerbate the condition during the treatment period. For the injection therapy, the patient was in supine position with elbow in 90° flexion and supination supported by a pillow. Taking proper antiseptic precautions, a 25G needle was inserted perpendicular to the lateral condyle in line with the cubital fossa crease to bone, and 1 mL of 10mg/mL solution of Triamcinolone Acetate with 1ml of lidocaine 2% was injected around the junction of tenoperiosteum. The Ultrasound Therapy was performed according to the standard guidelines.¹¹ Each patient received a total of eight sessions of ultrasound therapy during the first 4 weeks of treatment with twice weekly sessions. The patient was supine, with elbow in 90° flexion and supination. 3MHz continuous ultrasound therapy was given using a 0.5 transducer to the junction of tenoperiosteum for five minutes. The efficacy of the treatment modalities was evaluated at 1-week and 6-week follow-ups using the Patient-Rated Tennis

Elbow Evaluation (PRTEE) questionnaire. The pain in the affected elbow was scored out of 50, using the first part of PRTEE questionnaire. The functional disability was scored out of 100 using the second part of PRTEE questionnaire. Data entry and statistical analysis was done using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v. 25. Comparison of the outcome variables between the two modalities of treatment were made using Student t-Test. P-value ≤ 0.05 was kept as significant.

RESULTS

In this trial, we enrolled total 100 cases and segregated them in two equal groups. The mean age of patients enrolled in local steroid injection group was 40.64 ± 11.96 years while in therapeutic ultrasound group was 38.46 ± 11.20 years. In local steroid injection group, there were 53 (53.0%) men and 47 (47.0%) women. In therapeutic ultrasound group, there were 49 (49.0%) men and 51 (51.0%) women. The detail of mean height, weight and BMI of patients are given in table below. There were few patients who already received treatment for lateral epicondylitis, out of which 56 (56%) were segregated to local steroid injection group and 40 (40%) were segregated to therapeutic ultrasound group. Table I At baseline, the mean pain score was observed as 40.33 ± 5.83 in local steroid injection group while 38.79 ± 6.03 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value >0.05). After 6 weeks of treatment, the mean pain score was observed as 11.35 ± 4.89 in local

steroid injection group while 16.75 ± 4.33 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value <0.05) and local steroid injection showed better control over pain score. At baseline, the mean functional disability score was observed as 44.75 ± 8.97 in local steroid injection group while 44.85 ± 8.43 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value >0.05). After 6 weeks of treatment, the mean functional disability score was observed as 15.55 ± 3.70 in local steroid injection group while 19.46 ± 3.80 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value <0.05) and local steroid injection showed better control over functional disability score. At baseline, the mean usual activities score was observed as 29.72 ± 6.29 in local steroid injection group while 29.26 ± 5.72 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value >0.05). After 6 weeks of treatment, the mean usual activities score was observed as 7.76 ± 3.66 in local steroid injection group while 11.44 ± 2.54 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value <0.05) and local steroid injection showed better control over usual activities score. At baseline, the mean overall score was observed as 114.80 ± 14.29 in local steroid injection group while 112.90 ± 11.32 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value >0.05). After 6 weeks of treatment, the mean overall score was observed as 34.66 ± 7.09 in local steroid injection group while 47.65 ± 6.47 in therapeutic ultrasound group (p-value <0.05) and local steroid injection showed better control on overall score. Table II

Table I: Basic demographics of patients enrolled in the trial (n = 200)

	Local steroid injection	Therapeutic ultrasound
n	100	100
Age (years)	40.64 ± 11.96	38.46 ± 11.20
Gender	53 (53.0%)	49 (49.0%)
Male	47 (47.0%)	51 (51.0%)
Female		
Weight (kg)	76.11 ± 10.47	78.83 ± 12.00
Height (m)	1.68 ± 0.11	1.68 ± 0.11
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.07 ± 4.45	27.94 ± 4.15
History of smoking	56 (56%)	59 (59%)
Previous treatment received	56 (56%)	40 (40%)

Table II: Comparison of pain score, functional disability, usual activities score and overall score in both trial groups

	Local steroid injection	Therapeutic ultrasound	p-value
n	100	100	
Pain score at baseline	40.33 ± 5.83	38.79 ± 6.03	0.068
Pain score after 6 weeks	11.35 ± 4.89	16.75 ± 4.33	0.000
Functional disability score at baseline	44.75 ± 8.97	44.85 ± 8.43	0.935
Functional disability score after 6 weeks	15.55 ± 3.70	19.46 ± 3.80	0.000
Usual activities score at baseline	29.72 ± 6.29	29.26 ± 5.72	0.589
Usual activities score after 6 weeks	7.76 ± 3.66	11.44 ± 2.54	0.000
Overall score at baseline	114.80 ± 14.29	112.90 ± 11.32	0.298
Overall score after 6 weeks	34.66 ± 7.09	47.65 ± 6.47	0.000

DISCUSSION

Repetitive microtrauma and severe strain on the extensor carpi radialis brevis muscle result in lateral epicondylitis, a chronic aseptic inflammatory disease. The most common reason for elbow musculoskeletal pain syndrome is this, which results in severe discomfort and upper limb function limitations. In our study, at baseline, the mean pain score was 40.33 ± 5.83 vs. 38.79 ± 6.03 (p-value >0.05) that was reduced to 11.35 ± 4.89 vs. 16.75 ± 4.33 after 6 weeks, respectively (p-value <0.05). At baseline, the mean functional disability score was 44.75 ± 8.97 vs. 44.85 ± 8.43 (p-value >0.05) that was reduced to 15.55 ± 3.70 vs. 19.46 ± 3.80 after 6 weeks, respectively (p-value <0.05). At baseline, the mean usual activities score was 29.72 ± 6.29 vs. 29.26 ± 5.72 (p-value >0.05) that was reduced to 7.76 ± 3.66 vs. 11.44 ± 2.54, respectively (p-value <0.05) after 6 weeks. At baseline, the mean overall score was 114.80 ± 14.29 vs. 112.90 ± 11.32 (p-value >0.05) that was reduced to 34.66 ± 7.09 vs. 47.65 ± 6.47, respectively (p-value <0.05) after 6 weeks.

Similarly, Murtezani et al., The objectives of therapy after a diagnosis are to control pain, preserve range of motion, preserve strength and flexibility, and progressively increase endurance. The Patient-Rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation (PRTEE) questionnaire is a methodical way to monitor pain and functional impairment, University Clinical Centre of Kosovo, on 49 patients with epicondylitis. The study compared the Ultrasound & Exercise group (n = 25) with the corticosteroid injection group (n = 24).

Participants in the ultrasound group were 51.6 ± 6.7 years old, with 64% males, while the corticosteroid injection group had a mean age of 51 ± 6.2 years, with an equal gender distribution (50% males). At the six-week follow-up, the corticosteroid injection group showed lower PRTEE Pain Score (8.4 ± 3.5 vs 14.2 ± 5.8, p < 0.001) and PRTEE Function Disability Score (12.2 ± 6.4 vs 14.6 ± 5.5, p < 0.001) compared to the ultrasound therapy group.¹²

Research published in 2023 comparing the results of Platelet rich plasma and corticosteroid injection showed that at 3 months, average score of VAS in steroid group was 2.73 ± 1.48 and it was 2.53 ± 1.82 SD in PRP group (P=0.451). At 6 months, VAS average score was noted significantly decreased 2.11 ± 1.29 compared to steroid group was 4.83 ± 2.11 (P=0.001).¹³ The benefits of extracorporeal shockwave treatment (ESWT) over deep friction massage and ultrasonic therapy (US) for patients with lateral epicondylitis were investigated in another research conducted in 2024. ESWT is more beneficial for individuals with lateral epicondylitis, according to a between-group research, although both groups' PRTEE score comparisons at the third and seventh weeks of the intervention were significant (p < 0.001).¹⁴ In 2021, a research comparing transverse friction massage and ultrasonography in patients with persistent Achilles tendinopathy was published. However, following the third and sixth weeks of the intervention, the TFM (Transverse Friction Massage) group outperformed

the UST (Ultrasound treatment) group in every measure ($p < 0.05$).¹⁵

Ghandour et al., conducted a trial on 48 participants and found that before intervention, the mean pain scores, Nirschl stages, PFGS values, and pain across the lateral epicondyle were nearly identical ($P > 0.05$). After 1 week of injection, no difference was observed between both groups while after 6-48 weeks of treatment, significantly better findings were recorded for ultrasound guided injection ($P < 0.05$).¹⁶ Rahman et al., carried out a research in Dhaka and found that, after one and two weeks, nearly all of the patients in Local steroid injection group had little to no discomfort or soreness and had no trouble carrying objects. The VAS values were 4.15 ± 5.517 and 13.62 ± 6.503 , respectively. At one week, the pain and function of Therapeutic ultrasound group patients had improved somewhat, and at two weeks, they had improved somewhat. The corresponding VAS values were 25.57 ± 5.392 and 52.57 ± 7.80 . At one and two weeks, Additionally, with local steroid injection, tenderness significantly improved. They were, respectively, 1.60 ± 0.553 and 1.14 ± 0.335 for Therapeutic ultrasound group and 0.68 ± 0.616 and 0.02 ± 0.405 for Local steroid injection. At the conclusion of two weeks, the results were noteworthy. They come to the conclusion that local corticosteroid injections at the extensor origin provide faster functional improvement and greater pain and discomfort reduction than therapeutic ultrasound therapy for tennis elbow patients. In neither group were any of the patients monitored for long-term effectiveness.¹⁷

Ibrahim et al., found that shock wave therapy and corticosteroid injections both significantly reduced pain in a trial done at Behna University. The functional impairment criteria, such as PRTEE and rapid arm, shoulder, and DASH impairments, showed a highly significant change before and after two and four weeks of therapy. Similarly, after two weeks, the shock wave treatment group saw a statistically significant improvement; but, after eight and twelve weeks, there was an inversely insignificant difference in terms of VAS. Throughout the whole follow-up period, the PRTEE and Quick DASH tests revealed a statistically significant difference between the groups.¹⁸

This is in parallel to the study of Smidt et al., Thirteen trials were reported to evaluate the effectiveness of corticosteroid injection in treating lateral epicondylitis in comparison to local anaesthetic insertion, placebo administration, or another conventional treatment.¹⁹ In terms of pain alleviation, general improvement, and hand grip intensity, corticosteroid injections differed substantially from other therapeutic alternatives for short-term effects (≤ 6 weeks).^{20, 21}

Ismael et al., further saw a noteworthy decrease in pain and PRTEE totals during the 4- and 12-week follow-up periods.²² However, Lindenhovius et al. did not see any significant differences in pain and functional impairment ratings between corticosteroid injection and placebo insertion in either the short-term or long-term follow-up.²³ Newcomer et al., We observed no appreciable differences between the steroid infusion group and the placebo insertion group, even in the short term, in the VAS or functional outcomes.²⁴ These findings concur with those of Pettrone and McCall, who discovered that individuals with lateral epicondylitis who underwent therapeutic ultrasonography saw a highly significant reduction in pain severity.²⁵

CONCLUSION

Thus, the effect of local steroid injection is better than therapeutic ultrasound in reducing pain and improving functionality of elbow joint. Now in future, we will implement the use of local steroid injection for lateral epicondylitis instead of going for less effective therapeutic techniques or treatments.

FUNDING

For this research, no specific grant was attained from any funding agency in the public, commercial or non-profit sectors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are thankful Brig Dr Fayyaz Orfi for his support and guidance throughout our research which was very helpful to us in completion of our research project. We are also thankful to the whole surgical team as well as the study participants who have

helped us thoroughly in addressing this public health problem and conduct this research.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

ARA: Conception and design, acquisition of data, article writing, statistical analysis, proofreading

MIZ: Conception and design, acquisition of data, article writing, statistical analysis, proofreading

TA: Conception and design, acquisition of data, article writing, statistical analysis, proofreading

SK: Conception and design, article writing, statistical analysis, proofreading, acquisition of data

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